

Studies in Spiro-heterocycles. Part-XII. Synthesis of some Fluorine containing Spiro[3*H*-indole-3,4'(4*H*)-pyrano[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine]-2,5',7'(1*H*)-triones as CNS Agents

KRISHNA C. JOSHI*, RENUKA JAIN and KANTI SHARMA

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004

and

S. K. BHATTACHARYA and R. K. GOEL

Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005

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Several new fluorine containing spiro[3*H*-indole-3,4'(4*H*)-pyrano[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine]-2,5',7'(1*H*)-triones were synthesised by the Michael reaction of 3-(carboethoxycyano/dicyano)methylene-indol-2-ones with barbituric acid; the former being obtained from indole-2,3-dione and malononitrile/ethyl cyanoacetate. The compounds were characterised by ir, pmr, ^{19}F nmr, ^{13}C nmr and mass spectral studies. Representative compounds were tested on mice for CNS activities (analgesic and anticonvulsant) and the effects were also observed against amphetamine induced stereotypy on conditioned avoidance response and on potentiation of pentobarbitone sodium hypnosis.

Of the various heterocyclic systems, the indole nucleus has been reported as a common denominator of psychotropism and is of great value in the field of medicine and biochemistry^{1,2}. The pyran nucleus has been found to be associated with CNS and fungicidal activities^{3,4}. Some derivatives have been found to act as wide spectrum pesticides⁵. It has been observed that pyranopyrimidines show herbicidal activity in wheat and soyabeans⁶. Further, if the indole 3-carbon is in the form of a spiro-atom, the compounds exhibit enhanced biological activities. Keeping these observations in view, the title compounds were synthesised during our comprehensive programme of developing new biologically active organofluorine compounds.

The reaction of fluorinated indole-2,3-diones⁷⁻⁹ with ethyl cyanoacetate/malononitrile in presence of piperidine resulted in the formation of 3-(carboethoxycyano/dicyano)methylene-indol-2-ones which underwent Michael reaction with barbituric acid to afford the spiro compounds¹⁰ (Scheme 1).

In the ir spectra of compound 2a, a weak band at 1610 cm^{-1} (C=C) appeared and the C=O absorption of 1 disappeared. In the ir spectrum of 3a revealed ν_{max} 3370, 3150 (NH₂, NH), 2200–2180 (CN), 1720, 1690 and 1670 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ (pmr) 12.2 (6'NH), 10.4 (1NH), 7.3–7.1 (2'NH₂) and 7.1–6.7 (ArH). The ^{19}F nmr spectra showed signal at $\delta -112$ ppm due to fluorine attached to the benzene ring of indole. Further, the structure of 3a has also been confirmed on the basis of ^{13}C nmr and mass spectra, δ 204 (C-7'), 177 (C-5'), 161 (C-2), 157 (C-3'CN), 153 (C-2'), 150 (C-8'a), 148 (C-4'a), 143 (C-3'), 141, 132, 128, 123, 121 and 116 ppm's (aromatic carbons, C-5, 7a, 3a, 4, 6 and 7) and 109 ppm (C-3), (M^+) at m/e 341.

Scheme 1

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in open glass capillaries and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, ^1H nmr spectra on a Jeol FX 90Q spectrometer (89.55 MHz) using TMS as external reference and on a Perkin-Elmer RB-12 spectrometer (60 MHz) using DMSO-*d*₆ as solvent and ^{13}C nmr and ^{19}F nmr spectra on a Jeol FX 90Q spectrometer taken in DMSO-*d*₆ at 22.49 and 84.25 MHz, respectively; hexafluorobenzene ($\delta -162.9$ ppm) being used as external reference in the latter case. The mass spectra were recorded on MS-30 and MS-50 Kratos mass spectrometer operating at an ionisation potential of 70 eV.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF 3-(CARBOETHOXYCYANO/DICYANO)METHYLENE-INDOLE-2-ONES (2)

Compd. no.	X	R	R'	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	Nitrogen % : Found/(Calcd.)
2a	5-F	H	CN	78	230	C ₁₁ H ₄ FN ₂ O	18.09 (18.17)
2b	5-F	H	COOEt	68	240	C ₁₃ H ₆ FN ₂ O ₂	10.73 (10.76)
2c	6-F	H	COOEt	62	155	C ₁₃ H ₆ FN ₂ O ₂	10.70 (10.76)
2d	6-F	H	CN	74	238	C ₁₁ H ₄ FN ₂ O	18.20 (18.17)
2e	4-CF ₃	H	CN	59	119	C ₁₁ H ₄ F ₃ N ₂ O	14.80 (14.82)
2f	5-F	COOH ₂	CN	60	175	C ₁₁ H ₆ FN ₂ O ₂	16.41 (16.47)
2g	5-F	CH ₂ N	CN	61	110	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ FN ₂ O ₂	13.20 (13.18)

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF SPIRO[3H-INDOLE-3,4'(4H)-PYRANO[2,3-d]PYRIMIDINE]-2,5',7'(1H)-TRIONES (3)

Compd. no.	X	R	R'	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	Nitrogen % : Found/(Calcd.)
3a	5-F	H	CN	82	235d	C ₁₅ H ₆ FN ₂ O ₄	20.50 (20.52)
3b	5-F	H	COOEt	80	231	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ FN ₂ O ₅	14.08 (14.05)
3c	6-F	H	COOEt	78	265	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ FN ₂ O ₅	14.02 (14.05)
3d	6-F	H	CN	81	275	C ₁₅ H ₆ FN ₂ O ₄	20.49 (20.52)
3e	4-CF ₃	H	CN	62	250	C ₁₅ H ₆ F ₃ N ₂ O ₄	17.60 (17.64)
3f	5-F	COOH ₂	CN	68	270d	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ FN ₂ O ₅	18.21 (18.27)
3g	5-F	CH ₂ N	CN	67	227	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ FN ₂ O ₅	19.12 (19.09)

Fluorinated indole-2,3-diones (1) : 5-Fluoroindole-2,3-dione ; 6-fluoroindole-2,3-dione and 4-trifluoromethylindole-2,3-dione were prepared by the literature method⁷⁻⁹.

3-(Carboethoxycyano/dicyano)methylene-2-oxindoles (2) : A solution of fluoroindole-2,3-dione (0.17 mol) and ethyl cyanoacetate/malononitrile (0.17 mol) in ethanol (150 ml) containing piperidine (0.2 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. After being chilled overnight, the resulting solid was filtered off and washed with a little ether and finally recrystallised from alcohol (Table 1).

Spiro [3H-indole-3,4' (4H)-pyrano[2,3-d]pyrimidine]-2,5',7'(1H)-triones (3) : A solution of 3-(carboethoxycyano/dicyano)methyleneindole-2-one (0.01 mol) and barbituric acid (0.01 mol) in ethanol was treated with piperidine (2 drops) and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 3 h. After the removal of EtOH the resulting solid was rinsed with dichloromethane and recrystallised from ethanol to colourless prisms¹⁰ (Table 2).

Biological activity : Some of the compounds were screened for their central nervous system activities. Studies were conducted on inbred strains of albino rats (100–150 g) and albino mice (20–30 g). The animals were fed on standard diet

and housed in colony cages at an ambient temperature of 25 ± 2°. The animals were fasted overnight before the experiment but had water *ad libitum*.

The drugs were suspended in 10% Tween 80 and the activities were recorded after 1 h, unless stated otherwise. The CNS activity was expressed by using the following parameters ; pentobarbitone sodium (25 mg/kg ; i.p.) hypnosis potentiating effect in mice¹¹, anticonvulsant effect in rats against maximal electroshock (MES)¹² and pentylenetetrazol induced convulsions¹³, analgesic effect in mice against thermic hot-plate stimulation method¹⁴, and spontaneous activity in rats seen with the help of photoactometer.

All the compounds showed potentiation of sodium pentobarbitone hypnosis in the dose of 100 mg/kg. The anticonvulsant activity was also shown by compounds 3a, 3d–f against MES test but none of them showed any protection against pentylenetetrazole induced convulsions. The spontaneous activity in rats was also reduced by compounds 3a–c and f to nearly 50% level. The results of anticonvulsant, hypnotic-potentiating and spontaneous activity effect are presented in Table 3.

Compounds 3a–c exhibited significant analgesic effect but compound b was more potent (*p* < 0.01).

TABLE 3—ANTICONSULSANT, HYPNOTIC-POTENTIATING AND SPONTANEOUS ACTIVITY EFFECT OF SPIRO[3H-INDOLE-3,4'(4H)-PYRANO[2,3-d]PYRIMIDINE]-2,5',7'(1H)-TRIONES (3)

Compd. no.	Dose mg/kg (i.p.)	Rat MES %	Rat Anticonvulsant PT ₅₀	Mice hypnosis min	Rat SA after 1 h %
3a (X=5-F, R=H, R ¹ =CN)	100	60 ^b	0	43.4 ± 7.6 ^a	55.1
3b (X=5-F, R=H, R ¹ =COOEt)	100	20	0	47.8 ± 11.2 ^a	44.8
3c (X=H, R=H, R ¹ =CN)	100/50 ^d	20	0	45.8 ± 9.1 ^a	90.7
3d (X=5-F, R=COCH ₃ , R ¹ =CN)	100-50 ^d	80 ^c	0	40.2 ± 8.2 ^a	81.2
3e (X=4-CF ₃ , R=H, R ¹ =CN)	150-50 ^d	60 ^b	0	45.5 ± 6.9 ^a	66.9
3f (X=6-F, R=H, R ¹ =COOEt)	100	60 ^b	0	60.0 ± 11.2 ^a	44.1
Control		0	0	17.5 ± 7.9	100

^d Dose used for MES ; n=10 , P=^a ≤0.05, ^b ≤0.02 and ^c ≤0.005.

TABLE 4—ANALGESIC ACTIVITY OF SPIRO[3H-INDOLE-3,4'(4H)-PYRANO[2,3-d]PYRIMIDINE]-2,5',7'(1H)-TRIONES (3)

Compd. no.	Dose (mg/kg)	Increase in latent period of hot-plate response			
		15 min	30 min	45 min	60 min
3a (X=5-F, R=H, R ¹ =CN)	100	5.0 ± 3.0	3.6 ± 1.9	6.4 ± 2.8	6.4 ± 2.9 ^a
3b (X=5-F, R=H, R ¹ =COOEt)	100	3.0 ± 1.0 ^a	3.1 ± 0.8 ^b	4.3 ± 1.5 ^a	2.1 ± 0.6 ^b
3c (X=H, R=H, R ¹ =CN)	100	0.5 ± 0.9	0.9 ± 0.8	0.8 ± 0.8	1.2 ± 1.0
3d (X=5-F, R=COCH ₃ , R ¹ =CN)	100	6.7 ± 0.6	0.9 ± 0.7	1.8 ± 0.9	1.1 ± 0.9
3e (X=4-CF ₃ , R=H, R ¹ =CN)	100	1.3 ± 0.7	1.2 ± 0.8	1.0 ± 0.3 ^a	1.0 ± 0.6
3f (X=6-F, R=H, R ¹ =COOEt)	100	0.4 ± 0.4	1.5 ± 0.8	0.6 ± 0.6	1.3 ± 0.8

n=6 : values are mean ± S.E. ; P=^a ≤0.5 and ^b ≤0.01.

The results are shown in Table 4. LD₅₀ was not determined but there was no mortality at the dose of 100 mg/kg (i.p.) upto 24 h.

From the psychopharmacological evaluation the following conclusions can be drawn. Our observation indicate that compounds 3a, 3b, and 3d-f are potent whereas compound c is nearly inactive. From the structure we see that compound c is non-fluorinated whereas the rest are fluorinated. The data thus confirm that the presence of fluorine in a compound helps in enhancing its biological activity.

In case of the analgesic activity 3d is not effective as the others, where the hydrogen of NH (indole ring) is replaced by COCH₃ group indicating thereby that the replacement of active hydrogen by acyl group decreases the activity.

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